

**MODERATING INFLUENCE OF GOVERNMENT POLICY ON RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN
ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION AND BUSINESS START-UP OF UNDERGRADUATE
BUSINESS EDUCATION STUDENTS IN NORTH EAST, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The study aimed at determining the moderating influence of government policy on relationship between Entrepreneurship Education and Business Start-Up of Undergraduate Business Education students in North East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. Survey research design was used for the study. The area of the study is North east geopolitical zone of Nigeria and the population of the study comprised of 998 final year undergraduates' business education students. Total population sampling technique was used for the study. Instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled Moderating Influence of Government Policy on Relationship between Entrepreneurship Education and Business Startup (MIGPRBEEBS). The instrument used in this study was validated by three (3) experts, Reliability of the instrument was determined through Cronbach Alpha to test the internal consistency of the instrument and a reliability coefficient of .823 was obtained. The data were collected by the researcher assisted by three (3) research assistants. Data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS, 25). Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Regressions was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of confidence. The study revealed that entrepreneurial status, entrepreneurial mind-set, economic motivation have positive and significant influence on business start-up of undergraduate business education students. Based on this the study recommended among others that, National University Commission (NUC) should put in place every mechanism that will increase and motivate the development of Entrepreneurial status, Entrepreneurial mind-set, Economic motivation for business start-up of undergraduate business education students of federal universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Keywords; Business start up, Entrepreneurship, Government, Moderating, Policy

Introduction

The goal of Entrepreneurship education is in line with that of the National Policy on Education FRN (2013) which emphasized on developing intellectual capacity and values for the individual survival that will provide enabling environment to acquire both physical and intellectual skills for self-reliance and becoming useful members of the society. Similarly, Aliu (2014) stated that Entrepreneurship Education is learning directed towards developing in young people those skills, competencies, understandings, and attributes which equip them to be innovative, and training them to identify, create, initiate, and successfully manage personal and or community business, and work

opportunities, including working for them. This new paradigm has enabled the next generations to see things from a different perspective. Rather than hunt for opportunities in the job markets, they create a mind set to develop entrepreneurship capabilities and self-made wealth, (Fauziah, 2012).

Today's realities indicate that there is no government of any country that can absolutely provide job to absorb all graduates from her tertiary institutions. This means that there is need for a change in the mindset of graduates from the look for job syndrome to create job mentality in order to actualize their educational aspirations (Jiang & Sun, 2015) advocates that tertiary education students or graduates should demonstrate a high sense of responsibility in order to take advantage of the entrepreneurial revolution.

Therefore, from the foregoing discussion, it can be deduced that literature's from several studies have shown that the aim of entrepreneurship education in the Nigerian universities is defeated because after undergoing entrepreneurship education training in the universities in order to instilled in them to become self reliant after graduation, the students after graduation continue to roam about looking for a white collar jobs which is not readily available. Because of these this study would introduce government policy as a moderator to moderate the influence on relationship between entrepreneurship education and business start-up of undergraduate business education students in universities in North east, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the moderating influence of Government policy on relationship between entrepreneurship education and business start-up of undergraduate business education students in Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the influence of entrepreneurial status on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria
2. Determine the influence of entrepreneurial mind-set on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria
3. Examine the influence of economic motivation on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria

Research Questions

In line with the specific objectives the research questions are;

1. What is the influence of entrepreneurial status on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of entrepreneurial mind-set on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria?
3. What is the influence of economic motivation on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho₁: Entrepreneurial status does not significantly influence business start-up of undergraduate business education student of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria

Ho₂: Entrepreneurial mind-set does not significantly influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria

Ho₃: Economic motivation does not significantly influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria

Literature Review

The theory of social changes was developed by Everret Hagens in the year 1963 as an endeavour to explain how individual change their social status in order to gain societal respect. The core notion that drives this sociological theory is that when an individual feel that they are no longer respected by the society, they tend to implement innovative ways by means which the social status can get positively transformed. This desire to change the prevailing social status can be indicated as the acquired tendency of an individual to become an entrepreneur.

Therefore, theory of social changes is related to this study because it deals with how individual change their social status in order to gain societal respect, that can lead to entrepreneurial motivation such as innovation that also lead new venture creation. Also, business startup success is better understood by recognizing the entrepreneurial status of an individual success as entrepreneurs.

To be able to perform the whole range of tasks at different levels of uncertainty while creating, discovering or recognizing opportunity and creating a venture, entrepreneurs ought to possess the ability and mind set to match decision making mode to the nature of the task. Entrepreneurs with the entrepreneurial mind set are characterized by their ability to form and retrieve entrepreneurial knowledge structures or scripts, each pertaining to a distinct type of opportunity (Hynie & Shepherd, 2009).

The socio-cultural factors are those which have an effect on entrepreneurial activities that relate to both society and cultural matters. These include child rearing practices, cross cultural difference, cultural deprivation, cultural change, ethnic values, family structure, kingship structure, and regional differences (Onodugo & Onodugo, 2015). Entrepreneurs require financial support to diversify their start-up risks, obtain the start-up capital and finance growth and expansion. In many developing and emerging economies there are only few sources for financing and entrepreneurs might be prevented from starting a business as they do not receive the required finances (Juliane & Julia, 2014).

Methodology

Design of the Study

The Research Design for this study was descriptive survey design.

Area of the Study

The study was carried out in North-east Geo-political zone of Nigeria, which comprises six (6) states namely; Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe states respectively.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises all the 998 final year undergraduate Business Education students that acquired mandatory training on entrepreneurship education from the three selected Federal Universities in the North-East.

Sample and Sampling Technique

However, three Federal Universities that are offering business education were selected as the sample for this study and total population sampling technique was used for the purpose of this study.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used in this study for the data collection was a self-developed questionnaire by the researcher. The questionnaire is titled Moderating Influence of Government Policy on Relationship between Entrepreneurship Education and Business Startup (MIOGPORBEEABS).

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument used in this study was subjected to face and content validation. The validation was conducted by three experts, from the department of vocational and technology education, Faculty of Technology Education of the Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi.

Reliability of the Instrument

Data collected were subjected to Cronbach Alpha reliability index which was used to test and establish the internal consistency of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument showed that all the measurement items in the scale were satisfactory for the study.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher with the help of three (3) trained research assistants each from the universities administered nine hundred and ninety eight (998) questionnaire to the target respondents and nine hundred (900) were retrieved representing almost 90%.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the study were coded into Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS, 25). The package was used to run descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation for answering all the research questions (1-3). However, regression analysis was used to test all the null hypothesis (1-3) in order to determine the moderating effects of the independent variable on the dependent variables and the null hypotheses $H_{O1} - H_{O3}$ were tested at 0.5% level of significant

Decision Rule

However in order to answer the research questions, the researcher used Modified 4 points mean rating scale for measuring the variables and the decision rule was based on interval scale used as follows; 1.00 to 1.49 (strongly disagree); 1.50 to 2.49 (disagree); 2.50 -3.49 (agree); and 3.50 – 4.00 (strongly agree). In the test of null hypotheses, regressions analysis was used at 0.05 level of confidence and the decision rule was based on p-value, when the p-value was found to be less than the alpha value (0.05) the hypothesis was rejected and when the p-value was found to be greater than the alpha value, the hypothesis was accepted.

Results and Discussions

Research Question One

What is the influence of entrepreneurial status on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Entrepreneurial Status of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria

Items	N	M	SD	Decision
1. I enjoy thinking of original plan on which to work on a business venture	900	3.24	.861	Agreed
2. If I believe in business idea no obstacle will prevent me making it happen	900	3.09	.872	Agreed
3. I do not bother taking risk if the business is profitable	900	3.13	.904	Agreed
4. I try very hard to improve on my past business performance	900	3.15	.864	Agreed
5. I prefer to work in business venture that require skills	900	3.08	.903	Agreed
6. Need for achievement	900	3.43	.826	Agreed
7. In my own business I try to be my own boss	900	3.19	.838	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.19	.516	Agreed

Table 1 presented the output of descriptive statistics with regard to the research question (1) the result indicated that, the mean scores of entrepreneurial status items are ranging from 3.09 to 3.43. The grand mean of entrepreneurial status is 3.19 with a standard deviation of .516. The result indicated that entrepreneurial status influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Research Question Two

What is the influence of entrepreneurial mind-set on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of entrepreneurial mind-set of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria

Items	N	M	SD	Decision
1. I feel confident about my business abilities	900	3.24	.844	Agreed
2. I accomplish whatever business I started	900	3.09	.871	Agreed
3. I have seriously thought about starting my own business	900	3.18	.888	Agreed
4. I would rather innovate than continue to do the same old thing	900	3.11	.916	Agreed
5. I don't want someone to be in control of my own destiny	900	3.15	.931	Agreed
6. Life's challenges are opportunities for personal growth	900	3.13	.870	Agreed
7. Most people think I'm a strong leader	900	3.02	.906	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.13	.549	Agreed

Table 2 presented the output of descriptive statistics with regard to the research question (2) the result indicated that, the mean scores of entrepreneurial mind-set items are ranging from 3.02 to 3.24. The grand mean is 3.13 with a standard deviation of .549. The result indicated that entrepreneurial mind-set influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Research Question Three

What is the influence of economic motivation on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of economic motivation of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria

Items	N	M	SD	Decision
1. I have the desire to establish business to earn more money	900	3.24	.846	Agreed
2. I aspire to build a great fortune in business	900	3.13	.830	Agreed
3. I always long for independence	900	3.14	.879	Agreed
4. I always aspire for financial recognition	900	3.08	.859	Agreed

5. I have the desire to continue with my family business	900	3.14	.871	Agreed
6. I'm not satisfied with a paid salary job	900	3.05	.902	Agreed
7. I desire for self-actualization	900	3.17	.870	Agreed
8. Provide job for the family	900	3.16	.865	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.14	.511	Agreed

Table 3 presented the output of descriptive statistics with regard to the research question (3) the result indicated that, the mean scores of economic motivation items are ranging from 3.05 to 3.24. The grand mean of economic motivation is 3.14 with a standard deviation of .511. The result indicated that economic motivation influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis One

Entrepreneurial status does not significantly influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Table 4: Regression analysis on the influence of entrepreneurial status on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Variable	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-Value	p-Value	Decision
Entrepreneurial status	.559	20.132	.000	Rejected

The result of regression analysis in table 4 indicated that entrepreneurial status has a significant influence on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria (β .559; $t=20.132$; $p=0.000$). The result implies that entrepreneurial status significantly influenced business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Entrepreneurial mind-set does not significantly influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Table 5: Regression analysis on the influence of entrepreneurial mind-set on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Variable	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-Value	p-Value	Decision
Entrepreneurial mind-set	.499	17.154	.000	Rejected

Null hypothesis two which stated that, entrepreneurial mind-set does not significantly influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria was rejected based on the result documented in table 5 that entrepreneurial mind-set has significant influence on business start-up of undergraduate business education students (β .499; $t=17.154$; $p=0.000$). Therefore, null hypothesis two was rejected.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Economic motivation does not significantly influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Table 6: Regression analysis on the influence of economic motivation on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria.

Variable	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-Value	Decision
Economic motivation	.549	19.586	.000	Rejected

Null hypothesis three which stated that, economic motivation does not significantly influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria was rejected based on the result documented in table 6 that that entrepreneurial motivation has significant influence on business start-up of undergraduate business education students (β .549; $t=19.586$; $p=0.000$). Therefore, null hypothesis three was rejected.

Summary of the Findings

The summary of the findings were presented as follows:

1. The result of research question one revealed that entrepreneurial status has significant influence on business start-up of undergraduate business education student and the result of corresponding null hypothesis indicated that entrepreneurial status as the independent variable (IV) has a significant influence on the dependent variable (DV) business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.
2. The result of research question two indicated that Entrepreneurial mind-set has significant influence on business start-up of undergraduate business education students and the result of corresponding null hypothesis two stated that, entrepreneurial mind-set as the independent variable (IV) has significant influence on dependent variable (DV)

business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

3. The result of research question three indicated that economic motivation has significant influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students and the result of corresponding null hypothesis three economic motivation as the independent variable (IV) has significant influence on dependent variable (DV) business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal Universities in North-east, Nigeria. Therefore the null hypotheses was rejected.

Discussions of Findings

The result of research question one indicated that entrepreneurial status influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students and the result of corresponding null hypothesis one also indicated that entrepreneurial status influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal universities in North east, Nigeria significantly. The finding of the study was in line with the submission of Onodugo & Onodugo (2015) who stated that socio-cultural factors are those which have an effect on entrepreneurial activities that relate to both society and cultural matters. These include child rearing practices, cross cultural difference, cultural deprivation, cultural change, ethnic values, family structure, kingship structure, and regional differences.

The result of research question two indicated that Entrepreneurial mind-set influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students and the result of corresponding null hypothesis two also indicated that entrepreneurial mind-set influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal universities in North east, Nigeria significantly. The findings of the study is in line with the submission of Gustafsson (2004) who stated that entrepreneurs with an entrepreneurial mind set, while engaging in an opportunity identification task, are able to recognize the nature of the opportunity they confront and adapt their behaviour to the nature of the task.

The result of research question three indicated that economic motivation influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students and the result of corresponding null hypothesis three also indicated that economic motivation influence business start-up of undergraduate business education students of Federal universities in North east, Nigeria significantly. The findings of the research is in tandem with the study of Juliane & Julia (2014) they stated that Entrepreneurs require financial support to diversify their start-up risks, obtain the start-up capital and finance growth and expansion.

Conclusion

Today, Entrepreneurship education is paramount in the socioeconomic development of any nation world over because the main aim and objectives of introducing entrepreneurship education training and making it mandatory for undergraduate students in the universities in Nigeria is to prepare them to become self employed and self-reliant rather than job seekers. To this end, universities and government have put in place measures that help to promote entrepreneurship education training and business start-up. Based on the results obtained it was concluded that government policy moderates the influence of entrepreneurship education on business start-up of undergraduate business education students of federal universities in north-east, Nigeria positively and significantly. Effective and efficient government policy in moderating the relationship between entrepreneurship education and business startup

will help in ensuring the creation of employment opportunities and self-reliance among business education students in northeast, Nigeria. These will guarantee the actualization of mission and vision of making entrepreneurship education as mandatory and to also achieve the objectives of business education programme in universities in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. The National University Commission of the universities (NUC) should ensure monitoring and implementation of entrepreneurship education programme is geared towards business start-up of undergraduate business education student using government policy as a moderator on relationship between entrepreneurship education and business start up.
2. The policy makers should ensure in making policies that would be directed towards achieving entrepreneurship education for business start-up of undergraduate business education students using government policy as a moderator on relationship between entrepreneurship education and business start up.

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